

Free Methodist Church

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Entry tags: Religious Group, Christian Traditions, Methodist

A Christian denomination in the Wesleyan/Holiness tradition which broke away from the Methodist Episcopal Church in 1860. The major issue leading to the split concerned disagreements over slavery. The Methodist Episcopal Church (MEC) still had many slaveholders after the schism in 1844 saw the creation of the Methodist Episcopal Church, South (MEC, S). Official church policy recognized slaveholding as sin, but in practice had accepted the reality of the practice and attempted to justify it under several theories (e.g., paternalism toward slaves, keeping slaveholders in the church). Roberts and other abolitionists saw this compromise as a violation of the ethical precepts of Christianity and their Wesleyan heritage (John Wesley had been an abolitionist in Britain). However, the direct cause of the formation of the Free Methodist Church was a series of political maneuvers in Roberts' home conference which saw Roberts and several other pastors expelled from the MEC. There is a split in the scholarship as to whether Robert's abolitionist views lead to the political maneuvers or was merely one view amongst many that angered important parts of the church's hierarchy (see Snyder, 406-7). Upon establishing the new denomination, Roberts ended the practice of 'pew renting' by which wealthy individuals could 'rent' a pew in church with better visibility, both for and of themselves. He also ended instrumental music in churches, not on grounds against such music, but against the practice of paying trained musicians out of the church's funds which could have gone to other needs. Like much of the holiness tradition of the nineteenth century, simplicity was a virtue. Currently, the church has less than 100,000 members in the United States but totals more than one million total members worldwide. It is episcopal in organization with three bishops, each based in the USA. The church is connected to five universities in the United States: Roberts Wesleyan in New York, Spring Arbor in Michigan, Greenville University in Illinois, Central Christian University in Kansas, and Seattle Pacific in Washington; and another four internationally. The church is also affiliated with several non-denominational schools, including Azusa Pacific in California, and Asbury University and Asbury Theological Seminary in Kentucky. The Free Methodist Church fits nearly all definitions of 'evangelical' and members are generally theologically and politically conservative (in the USA) though the latter has more diversity among congregants. Among the other Wesleyan related churches, Free Methodists are most similar in theology to the Church of the Nazarene and the conservative (sometimes called 'traditional') wing of the United Methodist Church due to their teachings of both progressive and instantaneous sanctification at some point after justification. This experience has many names from different theologians but most use the terms 'Entire Sanctification' or 'Second work of grace' to describe it.

Date Range: 1860 CE - 2020 CE

Region: Free Methodist World Conference.

Region tags: Asia, Southeast Asia, Cambodia, Malaysia, Myanmar, Philippines, Thailand, East Asia, China, Hong Kong Special Administration Region, Japan, Republic of Korea, South Asia, Nepal, India, Sri Lanka, Europe, Southern Europe, Greece, Italy, Portugal, Spain, Eastern Europe, Bulgaria, Hungary, Romania, Ukraine, Northern Europe, United Kingdom of Great Britain and Northern Ireland, Western Europe, Belgium, France, North America, Canada, United States of America, Middle East, Oceania, Australia, Africa, Eastern Africa, Burundi, Ethiopia,

Kenya, Malawi, Mozambique, Rwanda, Uganda,
United Republic of Tanzania, Zambia, Zimbabwe,
Northern Africa, Egypt, Western Africa, Benin, Ghana,
Liberia, Togo, Southern Africa, Botswana, Namibia,
South Africa, Swaziland, Middle Africa, Angola,
Cameroon, Congo, Gabon, South America, Argentina,
Bolivia (Plurinational State of), Brazil, Chile, Colombia,
Ecuador, French Guiana, Paraguay, Peru, Uruguay,
Latin America and the Caribbean, Caribbean,
Dominican Republic, Haiti, Puerto Rico, Central
America, Costa Rica, Guatemala, Honduras, Mexico,
Nicaragua, Panama, Taiwan, Nigeria, Iraq, Jordan

Countries with Free Methodist Churches

Status of Participants:

- ✓ Religious Specialists
- ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources

Print sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Populist Saints: B.T. and Ellen Roberts and the First Free Methodists by Howard Snyder

Notes: Resource on the history of the Free Methodist Church including the lives of its founders (B.T. and Ellen Roberts) and the issues which led to the creation of a new Methodist movement out of the Methodist Episcopal Church.

Online sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: fmwconference.org
- Source 1 Description: Official website of the Free Methodist Church
- Source 1 URL: fmcusa.org
- Source 1 Description: Free Methodist Church- USA official website
- Source 2 URL: <https://fmcusa.org/resources/2019bod>
- Source 2 Description: Free Methodist Church- USA Book of Discipline

Notes: The Free Methodist Book of Discipline should not be confused with the United Methodist Book of Discipline.

Relevant online primary textual corpora (original languages and/or translations):

- Source 1 URL: https://www.ccel.org/ccel/roberts_bh/holiness.html
- Source 1 Description: A collection of sermons and other literary works by B.T. Roberts, compiled by his son Benson H. Roberts
- Source 1 URL: <https://historical.fmcusa.org/>
- Source 1 Description: The Maston Memorial Historical Center & Free Methodist Archive Website

Notes: Includes scanned images of B.T. Roberts' magazine "The Earnest Christian"; some audio links to

sermons and songs, and a collection of oral histories. The physical Archive has more material that has not been digitized.

General Variables

Membership/Group Interactions

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– Yes

↳ Is the cultural contact competitive:

– Yes

Notes: Between Christianity broadly and other religions in specific areas. Like other holiness groups, Free Methodists are also in low-level competition with mainline Christian denominations which holiness groups do not believe are committed in the right ways.

↳ Is the cultural contact accommodating/pluralistic:

– Yes

Notes: In secularized countries which have a history in the liberal tradition.

↳ Is the cultural contact neutral:

– Yes

Notes: In secularized societies with a general Christian background.

↳ Is there violent conflict (within sample region):

– Yes

Notes: Free Methodist churches and missionaries have been targeted in parts of Africa, for example- <https://www.nbcnews.com/news/us-news/american-missionary-captured-nigeria-rev-phyllis-sortor-released-n319006>

↳ Is there violent conflict (with groups outside the sample region):

– No

Does the religious group have a general process/system for assigning religious affiliation:

– Yes

↳ Assigned at birth (membership is default for this society):

– No

↳ Assigned by personal choice:

– Yes

Notes: Even in the case of infant baptism, the individual must accept or 'confirm' their own commitment to the church.

↳ Assigned by class:

– No

↳ Assigned at a specific age:

– No

↳ Assigned by gender:

– No

↳ Assigned by participation in a particular ritual:

– Yes

Notes: Baptism is required for membership, but baptism may have been performed by another denomination. Both infant and adult baptism is practiced. Free Methodist Book of Discipline, 2019, para. 124.

↳ Assigned by some other factor:

– No

Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members:

– Yes

↳ Is proselytizing mandated for religious professionals:

– No

Notes: There is no institutional mandate. However, as evangelicals, Free Methodists are mandated in so far as Jesus' command in Matthew 28:16-20. Religious professionals are expected to model such behavior to the laity when possible.

↳ Is proselytizing mandated for all adherents:

– No

Notes: There is no institutional mandate. However, as evangelicals, Free Methodists are mandated in so far as Jesus' command in Matthew 28:16-20.

↳ Is missionary work mandated for religious professionals:

– No

Notes: Long-term missionary work (in the sense of going to another geographical region/country) is carried out by religious professionals, but not all religious professionals are required to participate in long-term work.

↳ Is missionary work mandated for all adherents:

– No

Notes: However, short-term mission trips are strongly encouraged within the tradition.

↳ Is proselytization coercive:

– No

Does the religion have official political support

– No

Is there a conception of apostasy in the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: There is no unique institutional form of apostasy for Free Methodists, however, Wesleyan/Holiness denominations have a different view of grace than Calvinist based traditions and do not have the doctrine of the 'perseverance of the saints' (the P in standard 5-point Calvinist T.U.L.I.P acronym), and thus believers may 'fall away' into unbelief.

↳ Are apostates prosecuted or punished:

– No

Size and Structure

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– Estimated population, numeric: 1000000

Notes: Worldwide

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (% of sample region population, numerical):

– Estimated population, percentage of sample region: 0.0002

Scripture

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also “oral scriptures” (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– Yes

↳ Are they written:

– Yes

Notes: Free Methodists follow the Protestant standard of 66 books of the Bible- 39 Old Testament, 27 New Testament.

↳ Are they oral:

– No

↳ Is there a story (or a set of stories) associated with the origin of scripture:

– Yes

↳ Revealed by a high god:

– Yes

↳ Revealed by other supernatural being:

– No

↳ Inspired by high god:

– Yes

↳ Inspired by other supernatural being:

– No

↳ Originated from divine or semi-divine human beings:

– No

↳ Originated from non-divine human being:

– No

Architecture, Geography

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– No

Notes: Free Methodist structures are generally smaller and less ornate than their United Methodist cousins. This is due to smaller needs (in terms of average congregants) and less funding. Also, see Free Methodist Book of Discipline, 2019, pg. 5-7.

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– No

Is iconography present:

– No

Notes: Images from the Bible are used as decorations but do not reach the level of iconography. Crosses are empty, signifying the resurrection of Jesus.

Beliefs

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer “no” only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body. Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– Yes

Spirit-mind is conceived of as having qualitatively different powers or properties than other body parts:

– Yes

Belief in afterlife:

– Yes

Notes: Both heaven and hell are affirmed by Free Methodist teaching.

Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group:

– No

Notes: Though heaven is described in spatial terms, it is understood to be spiritual. The spatial reality of the New Heaven and New Earth is ambiguous and debated.

Reincarnation in this world:

– No

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– No

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– No

Are grave goods present:

– No

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

↳ As cenotaphs:

– No

↳ In cemetery:

– Yes

↳ Family tomb-crypt:

– No

↳ Domestic (individuals interred beneath house, or in areas used for normal domestic activities):

– No

↳ Other formal burial type:

– No

Supernatural Beings

Are supernatural beings present:

– Yes

↳ A supreme high god is present:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic:

– No

Notes: Though the Christian god is described in anthropomorphized terms, the tradition understands this to be metaphorical for human comprehension.

↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity:

– No

Notes: While there is some evidence that the ancient Israelite god may have originally been a sky god, Free Methodists do not generally ascribe to this claim.

↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld):

– No

↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god):

– No

↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:

– No

↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites:

– No

↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites:

– No

↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good:

– Yes

↳ Other feature(s) of supreme high god:

– Yes [specify]: Omnipotent, omnipresence, and omniscient

↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world:

– Yes

↳ The supreme god's knowledge is restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– No

- ↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:
 - No
- ↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region:
 - Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region:
 - Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):
 - Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):
 - Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):
 - Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god knows your basic character (personal essence):
 - Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god knows what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):
 - Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god has other knowledge of this world:
 - Yes [specify]: All past and future events.
- ↳ The supreme high god has deliberate causal efficacy in the world:
 - Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god can reward:
 - Yes
- ↳

↳ The supreme high god can punish:
– Yes

↳ The supreme high god has indirect causal efficacy in the world:
– Yes

↳ The supreme high god exhibits positive emotion:
– Yes

Notes: Christian teaching claims that 'God is love' (I John 4) and that all proper emotion is rooted in God's nature.

↳ The supreme high god exhibits negative emotion:
– Yes

Notes: The anger, or wrath, of God is a significant feature of the Old Testament (e.g. Exodus 32:8-10) and remains, to a slightly lesser degree, in the New Testament (e.g., Romans 1:18, Revelation)

↳ The supreme high god possesses hunger:
– No

↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural beings other than the high god:
– No

Notes: This is the most basic definition of idolatry which is condemned regularly in the Old Testament (The second of the Ten Commandments). The prohibition on idolatry is continued in the New Testament while simultaneously rejecting the notion that idols have any power (I Corinthians 8).

↳ The supreme high god possesses/exhibits some other feature:
– Yes [specify]: Omnipotence

↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living:
– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life:
– Yes

Notes: As with other holiness traditions, such communication is understood as 'promptings' from the Holy Spirit.

↳ In dreams:

– Yes

↳ In trance possession:

– No

↳ Through divination practices:

– No

↳ Only through religious specialists:

– No

↳ Only through monarch

– No

↳ Other form of communication with living:

– Yes [specify]: Free Methodists can say "God spoke to me through another person" where that person gives guidance or encouragement that seems to come from a supernatural source.

Notes: While not direct 'speech,' these occurrences are understood as God working through others, a common belief in Christianity, but especially in Wesleyan groups.

↳ Previously human spirits are present:

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings are present:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings can be seen:

– No

Notes: However, they may appear to certain individuals at certain times, especially in the biblical text (e.g. Jesus' birth narrative in Luke).

↳ These supernatural beings can be physically felt:

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world:

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– No

Notes: Within broader Christianity there are theological debates as to the degree of knowledge demons have but Free Methodist religious specialists are not usually involved in these debates.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge unrestricted within the sample region:

– Yes

Notes: Within broader Christianity there are theological debates as to the degree of knowledge demons have but Free Methodist religious specialists are not usually involved in these debates.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge unrestricted outside of sample region:

– Yes

Notes: Within broader Christianity there are theological debates as to the degree of knowledge demons have but Free Methodist religious specialists are not usually involved in these debates.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings knows your basic character (personal essence):

– Yes

- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings have other knowledge of this world:
 - Yes [specify]: Angels seem (according to biblical texts) to have knowledge of future events
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world:
 - Yes
- ↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion:
 - Yes
- ↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion:
 - Yes
- ↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger:
 - No
- ↳ These supernatural beings possess/exhibit some other feature:
 - No
- ↳ Mixed human-divine beings are present:
 - No
- ↳ Does the religious group possess a variety of supernatural beings:
 - Yes
- ↳ Organized by kinship based on a family model:
 - No
- ↳ Organized hierarchically:
 - Yes

↳ Power of beings is domain specific:

– No

↳ Other organization for pantheon:

– No

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– Yes

↳ There is supernatural monitoring of prosocial norm adherence in particular:

Prosocial norms are norms that enhance cooperation among members of the group, including obviously "moral" or "ethical" norms, but also extending to norms concerning honouring contracts and oaths, providing hospitality, coming to mutual aid in emergencies, etc.

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about taboos:

– No

Notes: Where 'taboo' is jargon within the field of religious studies; many pop culture taboos in the West (e.g., incest) are connected to Jewish and/or Christian teachings.

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of coreligionists:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other religions:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other polities:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about sex:

– Yes

↳ Adultery:

– Yes

Notes: See Free Methodist Church Book of Discipline 2019 para 3215.

↳ Incest:
– Yes

↳ Other sexual practices:
– Yes [specify]: Homosexuality; use of pornography

Notes: See Free Methodist Church Book of Discipline 2019 para 3215 and 3214, respectively.

↳ Supernatural beings care about lying:
– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about honouring oaths:
– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about laziness:
– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about sorcery:
– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about non-lethal fighting:
– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about shirking risk:
– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about disrespecting elders:
– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about gossiping:
– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about property crimes:
– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about proper ritual observance:

– No

Notes: While 'ritual' is used in the Free Methodist Book of Discipline- Chapter 8 is entitled 'The Ritual' which concerns sacraments, marriage, burial, and membership observances- the Jewish-Christian split on ritualistic observances (Acts 15) means that these are not divinely commanded rituals, but human guidelines for the group.

↳ Supernatural beings care about performance of rituals:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about conversion of non-religionists:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about economic fairness:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about personal hygiene:

– No

Notes: Free Methodists follow the hygienic practices of their culture.

↳ Supernatural beings care about other:

– Yes [specify]: God as creator implies a care for all of creation. In recent years, Free Methodists have shown more openness to environmental concerns.

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– Yes

↳ Is the cause or agent of supernatural punishment known:

– Yes

↳ Done only by high god:

– No

Notes: However, permission for other supernatural beings to mete out punishment is dependent upon the high god's allowance of such punishment (see Job 1-2; 2 Corinthians 12:7-9).

↳ Done by many supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle:

– Yes

Notes: The book of Proverbs is indicative of this teaching.

↳ Done by other entities or through other means [specify]

– No

↳ Is the reason for supernatural punishment known:

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:

– No

↳ Done to enforce group norms:

– No

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness:

– No

↳ Done randomly:

– No

Notes: Even if punishment seems random from a human perspective, Free Methodists (along with many other Christian groups) would attribute a 'deeper meaning' or 'higher purpose' that may not be comprehensible by the human mind.

↳ Other [specify]

– Yes

Notes: Free Methodists generally believe that supernatural punishment in this life is a result of sin (as with many Christian groups) or as a 'test' or challenge through which one can grow closer to God (as with many groups in the Holiness tradition).

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in the afterlife:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural punishments in the afterlife are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of mild sensory displeasure:

– No

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of extreme sensory displeasure:

– No

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation as an inferior life form:

– No

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation in an inferior realm:

– No

↳ Other [specify]

– Yes

Notes: Afterlife punishment is the understood as the absence of God with physical punishments understood as metaphorical.

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in this lifetime:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural punishments in this life are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of bad luck:

– No

↳ Punishment in this life consists of political failure:

– No

↳ Punishment in this life consists of defeat in battle:

– Yes

Notes: However, this teaching only applies to ancient Israel.

↳ Punishment in this life consists of crop failure or bad weather:

– Yes

Notes: However, this teaching only applies to ancient Israel.

↳ Punishment in this life consists of disaster on journeys.

– No

↳ Punishment in this life consists of mild sensory displeasure:

– No

↳ Punishment in this life consists of extreme sensory displeasure:

– No

↳ Punishment in this life consists of sickness or illness:

– Yes

Notes: However, this teaching only applies to ancient Israel and is contradicted by Jesus (John 9:1-34).

↳ Punishment in this life consists of impaired reproduction:

– No

↳ Punishment in this life consists of bad luck visited on descendants:

– No

↳ Other [specify]

– No

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– Yes

↳ Is the cause/purpose of supernatural rewards known:

– Yes

↳ Done only by high god:

– Yes

↳ Done by many supernatural beings:

– No

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle:

– No

- ↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:
 - No
- ↳ Done to enforce group norms:
 - No
- ↳ Done to inhibit selfishness:
 - No
- ↳ Done randomly:
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in the afterlife:
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural rewards in the afterlife are highly emphasized by the religious group:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of mild sensory pleasure:
 - No
- ↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of extreme sensory pleasure:
 - No
- ↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of eternal happiness:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of reincarnation as a superior life form:
 - No
- ↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of reincarnation in a superior realm:
 - No
- ↳ Other [specify]
 - No

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in this lifetime:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural rewards in this life are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of good luck:

– No

↳ Reward in this life consists of political success or power:

– Yes

Notes: However, this teaching only applies to ancient Israel.

↳ Reward in this life consists of success in battle:

– Yes

Notes: However, this teaching only applies to ancient Israel.

↳ Reward in this life consists of peace or social stability:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of healthy crops or good weather:

– Yes

Notes: However, this teaching only applies to ancient Israel.

↳ Reward in this life consists of success on journeys:

– No

↳ Reward in this life consists of mild sensory pleasure:

– No

↳ Reward in this life consists of extreme sensory pleasure:

– No

↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced health:

– No

↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced reproductive success:

– No

↳ Reward in this life consists of fortune visited on descendants:

– No

↳ Other [specify]

– Yes

Notes: Within the Holiness Tradition, there is a belief that God can sanctify an individual to the point where sinning is no longer a normal part of human life, though many theologians connected to the holiness tradition, most notably John Wesley, believe that such sanctification comes very late in life, but that the potentiality of such sanctification exists for all Christians. This differs from other Christian traditions which suggest that sinning is always part of the human condition and cannot be overcome in this life.

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present:

– Yes

↳ Is the messiah's whereabouts or time of coming known?

– No

Notes: Free Methodists take Jesus words in Matthew 24:36 at face value and have not engaged in messianic predictions.

↳ Is the messiah's purpose known:

– Yes

↳ Messiah is a political figure who restores political rule:

– No

↳ Messiah is a priestly figure who restores religious traditions:

– No

↳ Other purpose:

– Yes [specify]: The Messiah returns to establish the Kingdom of God on Earth and thus joins the political and priestly roles while also broadening them.

Norms and Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: See Free Methodist Book of Discipline 2019, para. 3010ff.

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:

– Yes

↳ What is the nature of this distinction:

– Present and clear

Notes: For example: Free Methodists hold that certain aspects of democratic society, while good, are not necessarily bound to religious morality. See Free Methodist Book of Discipline, 2019 para. 3331.

↳ Are specifically moral norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Specifically moral norms are implicitly linked to vague metaphysical concepts:

– No

↳ Specifically moral norms are explicitly linked to vague metaphysical entities:

– No

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked to impersonal cosmic order (e.g. karma):

– No

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked in some way to an anthropomorphic being:

– Yes

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked explicitly to commands of anthropomorphic being:

– Yes

↳ Specifically moral norms are have no special connection to metaphysical:

– No

↳ Moral norms apply to:

– All individuals (any time period)

Notes: With the understanding that how morality plays out may differ by culture but that the most generalized form of the moral command is universal.

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Honesty / trustworthiness / integrity:

– Yes

↳ Compassion / empathy / kindness / benevolence:

– Yes

↳ Mercy / forgiveness / tolerance:

– Yes

↳ Generosity / charity:

– Yes

↳ Selflessness / selfless giving:

– Yes

↳ Righteousness / moral rectitude:

– Yes

Practices

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence):

– Yes

↳ Monogamy (males):

– Yes

↳ Monogamy (females):

– Yes

↳ Other sexual constraints (males):

– Yes

Notes: Prohibition on homosexuality- Free Methodist Book of Discipline 2019 para 3215.

↳ Other sexual constraints (females):

– Yes

Notes: Prohibition on homosexuality- Free Methodist Book of Discipline 2019 para 3215.

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require fasting:

– No

Notes: However, fasting is considered a positive practice.

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods):

– No

Notes: However, abstinence from alcohol is encouraged. FM Book of Discipline, 2019, para 3213.

Does membership in this religious group require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– No

Notes: Euthanasia is also forbidden. Free Methodist Book of Discipline, 2019; para. 3222, C.

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of property/valuable items:

– No

Notes: Free Methodist churches do collect tithes and offerings (10% of one's income and more than that amount, respectively); however, failure to do so does not disqualify one in membership.

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of time (e.g., attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.):

– No

Notes: Time sacrifices in the form of church attendance, prayer, bible study, and service are expected of members, but failure to do so consistently does not disqualify one as a member.

Does membership in this religious group require physical risk taking:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require accepting ethical precepts:

– Yes

Notes: See Free Methodist Book of Discipline, 2019, para. 3000ff.

Does membership in this religious group require marginalization by out-group members:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household):

– No

Notes: However, many bible study groups are home based.

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

i.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale "ceremonies" and "festivals."

– No

Notes: There is a presumption that Free Methodists will attend church regularly (Free Methodist Book of Discipline, 2019, para. 3121), especially on particularly important days in the Christian calendar

(Christmas Eve, Easter).

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present:

E.g. special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification, etc.

– No

Notes: While not required, many Free Methodists do practice male circumcision on newborns.

Does the group employ fictive kinship terminology:

– Yes

Fictive kinship terminology universal:

– Yes

Notes: Following the New Testament, particularly the writings of Paul, Free Methodists have used 'brother' and 'sister' to refer to fellow congregants as well as 'children of God' as a self-referent. Such terminology is not mandated and may be just as connected to socio-cultural regions (e.g., the southern region of the United States) where many Christian denominations use similar terminology.

Fictive kinship terminology widespread:

– Yes

Fictive kinship terminology employed but uncommon:

– No

Society and Institutions

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– A state

Notes: The Free Methodist Church began in the United States but has spread into areas and groups which may be characterized as 'tribes.' However, the majority of Free Methodists live in areas characterized as 'states.'

Welfare

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized famine relief:

– Yes

Notes: Under the auspices of the "Bishops' Crisis Response Fund" which is used for many type of relief situations. <https://give.fmcusa.org/page.aspx?pid=1278>

Is famine relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized poverty relief:

– Yes

Notes: These groups exist at the level of the Free Methodist World Conference and are spread throughout different ministry areas, particularly missions. See Free Methodist Book of Discipline, 2019, 3221 A.

Is poverty relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm:

– No

Notes: Individual churches may support such organizations, but there is not a system at the national (USA) or World level for such support.

Is institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Education

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– Yes

Notes: <https://fmcusa.org/ministries/educational-institutions>

Is formal education restricted to religious professionals:

– No

Is such education open to both males and females:

– Yes

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Is extra-religious education open to both males and females:

– Yes

Bureaucracy

Do the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

– Yes

Notes: The Free Methodist Church is episcopal and operates under a system of bishops and district superintendents. However, this bureaucracy is minuscule when compared to the United Methodist Church.

Do the group's adherents interact with other institutional bureaucracies:

– Yes

Public Works

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– Yes

Notes: In the form of food 'banks' or 'pantries' at a local church level.

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question provide water management (irrigation, flood control):

– No

Notes: However, mission projects do occasionally deal with setting up irrigation systems.

Is water management provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

– No

Is transportation infrastructure provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Taxation

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

– No

Notes: Tithes are collected but are voluntary.

Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Enforcement

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized police force provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized judicial system provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

– No

Are the group's adherents subject to institutionalized punishment enforced by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Do the institutionalized punishments include execution:

– Yes

Do the institutionalized punishments include exile:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include corporal punishments:
– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include ostracism:
– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include seizure of property:
– Yes

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:
– No

Are the group's adherents subject to a formal legal code provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:
– Yes

Warfare

Does religious group in question possess an institutionalized military:
– No

Do the group's adherents participate in an institutionalized military provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:
– Yes

Are the group's adherents protected by or subject to an institutionalized military provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:
– Yes

Written Language

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:
– No

Is a non-religion-specific written language available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:
– Yes

Is a non-religion-specific written language used by the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Calendar

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:

– No

Notes: Free Methodist churches do follow the Catholic/Protestant liturgical calendar, but the laity may or may not be aware of the significance, other than Advent.

Is a formal calendar provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– No

Is food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Please characterize the forms/levels of food production [choose all that apply]:

– Large-scale agriculture (e.g., monocropping, organized irrigation systems)